

A NEW *CONUS* (GASTROPODA: CONIDAE) SPECIES FOUND IN HONDURAS

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Introduction:

«.....unlike other more homogeneous marine provinces, the Caribbean is a conglomerate of distinct pockets with often highly endemic faunas. There is now evidence that this mosaic pattern of faunas did not derive from a single ancestral province as originally formulated by WOODRING (1974), but from two distinct provinces, a «Caloosahatchian Province» in the North and a «Gatunian Province» in the South, which originally also included the eastern Pacific area (PETUCH, 1982). In the North the «Caloosahatchian Province» produced such endemic species as *Conus delessertii*, in the South the final closing of the isthmus of Panama gave rise to the development of trans-isthmian «cognate» species showing similarity, such as *Conus gladiator* in the eastern Pacific and *Conus mus* in the Caribbean.

The rise of the Panamanian Isthmus is not the only important event in the distant past; equally catastrophic were glacially-induced sea level fluctuations at the end of the Pliocene and during the Pleistocene. At one stage of low sea level the Caribbean region was cut into three more-or-less separate basins: the Gulf of Mexico; a basin comprised between Cuba in the North and a ridge of islands stretching from Yucatan to Jamaica in the South; and a third basin South of this ridge and further delimited by the arc of West Indian Islands. During these sea level fluctuations, with corresponding changes in water temperature, rapid speciation took place in the West Indian Islands, giving rise to the formation of such species complexes as that of *Conus cardinalis* and *Conus cedonulli*. In this connection it must be noted that some species of *Conus* such as widely distributed *Conus regius* have a free swimming veliger state (BANDEL, 1975), whereas other species such as members of the *Conus cedonulli* complex hatch at the late pediveliger stage and are unable to cross channels of deeper water (VON COSEL, personal communication 1983). Gene flow between closely related populations of these latter species can only take place when sea levels are low, and is interrupted again when sea levels come back up. The result is a complicated species complex, which may include various species, subspecies and forms».

The foregoing is an extract from the preamble to the superb series: «The Conidae of the Western Atlantic, Part I» by DANKER L. N. VINK (La Conchiglia, N. 186-187, September-October, 1984). It elucidates some background aspects on the occurrence of conid species in the tropical Caribbean area, which I am borrowing,

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because it serves as a very apt and succinct introduction to the discovery of yet another isolated population found to be endemic to Roatan Island, Honduras, made by TED KALAFUT, who provided the study material enabling a new taxon to be proposed hereunder.

Conus kalafuti n. sp.

Description: Shell small up to 15mm, obconic, with a spire consisting of six whorls, having a white double-whorled protoconch at its apex; surface of spiral volutions being flat except the last two being somewhat concave with a folded edge. The shoulder is angulate and sharply carinate, having sides which are flat and tapering down its length. The body whorl is smooth and glossy and its ground color is golden yellow, girdled by a white center band indistinctly tessellated with irregular brown spots. Some specimens are completely yellow without the maculated mid-section belt. The spire is off-white, decorated with brown vermiform strands in a radial pattern, with a narrow white zone overlapping the shoulder line. Occasionally, blotches and zigzag patches of white are stencilled on the body whorl. The aperture widens very slightly at the anterior end; its interior colored a nacreous yellowish tint. The periostracum is translucent and light brown.

Habitat: Always found in algae, exposed, on top of the coral rubble, below a depth of 35 to 40 feet. *C. daucus* Hwass, *C. kulkulcan* Petuch, *C. granulatus* Linnaeus *C. regius* Gmelin and *C. mus* Hwass are found in the vicinity, but not one is sympatric.

Type locality: N. W. Roatan Island (16.18 N 86.35 W) off the coast of Honduras, Caribbean Sea.

Holotype: 15x8mm deposited in the Museum Histoire Naturelle, Geneva, No. MHNG 987.111.

Paratypes: No. 1: 13.5 x 7.8mm deposited in the American Museum of Natural History, New York, No. 225977.

No. 2: 12.6 x 7.2mm

No. 6: 11.6 x 6.7mm

No. 3: 13.6 x 7.5mm

No. 7: 14.1 x 7.8mm

No. 4: 11.5 x 6.4mm

No. 8: 13.9 x 7.6mm

No. 5: 13.3 x 8.1mm

All paratypes retained by the author for subsequent distribution to other museums, except No. 7 and 8 which are in the coll. of TED KALAFUT.

Anatomy: Coloration was observed from a live specimen in tank. A radular scan is being made but was still not available at time of going to press.

Discussion: The new species is, structurally, very close to *Conus sahlbergi* da Motta & Harland, 1986, also an endemic species, but to Bahamas. Although equally of a small size, it attains up to 19mm in length. It has a low conic spire with a roseate protoconch, having eight spiral whorls, surface of which is flat except for the last two being slightly concave and etched with arcuate striae. However, it has a polychromatic range of variability from yellow to orange, white, purple and greenish-tan compared to the predominately golden yellow of the new species. It is also without maculations, whereas the new species has brown spiral markings and a spotted center band.

Conus daucus, Hwass in Bruguiere, 1792 found in the vicinity but not together, is another species with a profusion of color and pattern variability, whose distribution ranges widely from the Antilles to northern Brazil. Deep sea varieties attain sizes in excess of 50mm. The forms occurring in Roatan Island are mostly orange but sometimes lemon yellow with a bright pink protoconch. It has an intact midsection band of a lighter shade of its ground color and the spire, although depressed, is more concave than conic.

Conus mayaguensis Usticke, 1968 has a similar profile but the sides are more convex than flat. It has a color range of several pastel shades from orange, reddish brown, bright pink to olive-green. Most specimens are known from off the Atlantic and southern coast of Florida and off Yucatan. However, it does have a similar center band of white, spotted with brown markings, but otherwise is not difficult to tell apart from the new species.

Conus kulkulcan Petuch, 1980 although occurring nearby, is always found under rocks from 6 to 50 feet in a different part of the reef. It is strongly coronated at the shoulder, and the body whorl is heavily sculptured with pustulated spiral cords. Its color varies from bluish-grey, brown to rose-red, with a broader center band of white, with prominent brown markings. It attains lengths in excess of 36mm. Its distribution extends to Bahamas and the south-east coast of Cuba but with some variation in its pattern and coloration. Its periostracum is opaque and tufted.

Conus flavescens «Gray» Sowerby, 1834 is also colored yellow within its range of variation, but is cylindrical in shape by comparison, with a pyramidal spire and attenuated body whorl. It is not found in Honduras but occurs in the Bahamas, Florida, and into the Lesser Antilles.

No evidence can be found to associate *Conus kalafuti* specifically with any other already known species of the Caribbean region.

RESUMO

O autor descreve uma nova espécie do género *Conus* (Mollusca: Gastropoda), originária das Honduras.

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A

B

- A — *Conus kalafuti* n. sp. holotype (M.H.N.G. 987-111)
B — *Conus kalafuti* n. sp. holotype (M.H.N.G. 987-111)